

Cost, Advocacy, and a Mechanism for Transformation

The Proposed Power of Open Access Funds

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As paid open access becomes a mainstream academic practice, stakeholders must evaluate their role in the system. While open access advocates develop new ways to support the publication process and funding structure, commercial publishers continue to pivot to maintain their profit, relevance, and power in the publication system. This article provides the details of Montana State University's Open Access Author Fund as an evaluation of the service and its impact on the local publishing ecosystem. As stewards of publicly funded knowledge, it is essential to critically analyze each new publishing route before adopting and supporting it. Especially when models claim to transform the system, librarians need to understand how an action changes the system, for whom, and at what cost.

As open access (OA) publishing solidifies its position as a mainstream academic practice, there is extensive speculation about the future of scholarly communication and how a new system would be sustained financially.¹ There are numerous proposed methods of transforming the system of academic publishing.² They include Plan S,³ institutional repositories,⁴ article processing charges (APC), Read and Publish,⁵ and Read and Let Read.⁶ It is unlikely that actual transformation will occur without broad systemic adjustments. Even as OA advocates, academic authors, librarians, funders, and journals introduce innovations into publication processes and funding structures, commercial publishers pivot to maintain their profit, their relevance, and their power in the system.⁷

As an investigation of local efforts to support the transition to openly available research through financial support and normalizing OA publishing, this article provides the details of the Montana State University Library's Open Access Author Fund as an evaluation of the service and its impact on the local publishing ecosystem.

Literature Review

Profit

Open access to read and reuse literature is a goal that was formally laid out in the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) more than twenty years ago and much of the intervening time has been spent trying new processes to realize that goal.⁸ Commercial publishers initially saw OA as a threat to their profitability, but the rise of the APC introduced a new revenue stream that increased their income with little additional labor.

The practice of paid open access has gained mainstream prevalence as gold open access.⁹ Authors can pay to have their work published in fully OA journals or subscription-based journals that have a

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hybrid option. Journals that support gold OA levy charges to publish articles OA and do not charge a subscription fee to read those articles. This is a dramatic shift in the system of remuneration for the labor needed to review, publish, and disseminate research articles. Open access journals are sometimes mistaken for vanity or predatory publications, as they function with a similar payment model.¹⁰ Predatory journals are those that require payment without peer or editorial review and publish unscrupulously for profit. Although some OA journals are indeed predatory, many maintain rigorous publishing processes and have merely modified their source of revenue away from subscription charges. Predatory journals prey on those who cannot or do not see the difference.¹¹

Although the OA movement grew in response to the serials crisis to combat the unsustainable costs of journal subscriptions, APC-based open access models have not brought down costs. Instead, the move to APCs seems to represent an increase in revenue opportunities, not a reduction.¹² Rather than shifting the market toward a lower-cost and more financially sustainable or equitable model, APCs have broadened the types of pockets publishers can reach into to include research offices, individual authors, co-author's institutions, other university funding, and federal funding agencies.¹³ In this model, the customer is often separated from the cost of the transaction, so the price of an APC is not tied to traditional market conditions.¹⁴

APCs can cost more than one-hundred times the price of a single pay-per-view download.¹⁵ In 2021, for example, APCs for hybrid and pure OA journal articles in cardiology and cardiac surgery cost \$244–\$5,000 apiece.¹⁶ The same year, ecology journals with higher impact factors had higher APCs,¹⁷ and Nature-branded journals that offer a hybrid OA publishing route increased their APCs to \$11,900.¹⁸ The transaction is based on the concept that it costs thousands of dollars to publish a single article, though few publishers provide transparency around pricing or services.¹⁹ Further, though most publishers balk at the idea that they are double dipping, APCs for hybrid journals do not offset the subscription prices for most library subscribers.²⁰ The 2019 revision of Plan S suggests that APCs should be capped at an acceptable rate and provide transparent cost and price data, though what constitutes acceptable remains unclear.²¹

Relevance

Journals that have relied on subscription models to fund their operations have built a system that upholds their prestige based on a long-standing legacy.²² Hybrid publication options maintain the trustworthiness of the current system while allowing paying authors to provide open access to their research articles. Authors receive both the academic benefits of publishing in a trustworthy venue—including tenure, promotion, and advancement—and the benefits of publishing in an open manner—increased readership, increased citations, and a broader impact. Hybrid open access maintains the status quo of the academic publishing system by functioning within it, while adding benefit for both the publisher and the author.

Read and Publish deals, pre-paid OA deals, and other “subscription plus” deals maintain the existing financial structures of academic publishing, rather than shifting the economic landscape to a more equitable or sustainable model.²³ These deals also provide data to scholarly publishers who increasingly

operate as data analytics and analysis companies, further concentrating the industry. Aspici and Brand note that this push toward data analytics services will further consolidate the publishing market and that this move will limit the profitability of “pure journal publishers, starving them of the capital needed to compete effectively and innovate.”²⁴ Read and publish deals reinforce library ties to commercial publishers, reinforcing the budgetary conditions that significantly contributed to the current serials crisis.²⁵ These deals, rather than transforming the system, further entrench existing structures of power and prestige to maintain the relevance of a few multinational publishers.²⁶

Springer Nature, who pioneered both the APC and the transformative agreement, seeks to consolidate the “wild” funding sources to more effectively monitor and “harness” these funds.²⁷ This type of service further ties academic libraries to each such contract and reinforces the budget-bound model of providing access to research.

The Power to Transform

The lack of long-established, trustworthy new forms and types of digital scholarship discourages widespread acceptance of new initiatives relative to traditional scholarly venues.²⁸ Since greater access to published articles is both a public good²⁹ and a benefit for institutions, libraries and research offices have set up funds to pay APCs for hybrid and gold open access publication.³⁰ The funds serve to finance publications, promote OA publication, educate authors on journal selection, and assist in funder compliance. Optimistically, “open-access funds demonstrate an institution’s concrete support for reshaping the economics of scholarly communication,” but practically, we should consider the tangible evidence of that reshaping.³¹

Scholarly publishing is dependent on many shared layers of infrastructure and to sustainably change any aspect of the system, many players must be involved.³² Thus, it would be difficult for a single solution to change the whole landscape. Many of the current initiatives that attempt to transform the system rely on a pay-to-publish model, creating a deeper divide between institutions and scholars with funding and those without. Too often, those funding disparities can be discovered using national boundaries, further disadvantaging scholars and ways of knowing that are already negatively impacted by the centralization of knowledge production to northern, English-speaking countries.³³ Though publishers offer APC fee waivers (e.g., *eLife* 2021),³⁴ “the system is limited, shoddy, and patronizing—a charity band-aid on a broken system.”³⁵ For example, in ecology journals the availability of waivers is often unclear, lacks uniformity across publishers, and adds uncertainty to the publication process.³⁶ The benefits of these pay-to-publish models would appear to be concentrated in institutions and systems that already enjoy privileged circumstances.

As a bridge between traditional subscriptions as paid for by institutional libraries and a new, undetermined system that allows information to move freely across the internet as a public good, APCs have a role, though hopefully a limited one.³⁷ Intermediate solutions should not replace the long-term goals of a more financially sustainable, globally-equitable publication model.

Description of Program/Service

Motivation

In spring 2014, the Montana State University Library decided to dedicate a portion of their collections budget to develop a culture and practice of open access publication at the university. The amount of \$50,000 was designated in the library's Collection Development budget to provide funding for APCs. Based on the idea that the culture around academic publishing must change to inform practice and that researchers who understand that the mode of access is a separate consideration from the legitimacy of a journal are more inclined to change their behavior in the long-term, the library set up APCs as a part of the transition to open publishing.³⁸ Although libraries or research offices often pay these charges, separating the source of funding from the author, APCs seemed to be a reasonable short-term step in the process of changing the ecosystem and authority of scholarly journal publishing.³⁹ Initially a committee of faculty librarians, the Scholarly Communication Group (SCG), guided the development of the open access author fund. The SCG acknowledged that any system that lacks external regulation and where the funding and the demand are separate entities may devolve according to power structures and that our fund may contribute to the disconnect between the price of APCs and their value within the system of higher education.⁴⁰ The SCG decided that in order to function within the system to the benefit of our authors and to broaden the access to research, we would allocate funding with a reasonable cap. The SCG chose a limit of \$2,000 per author and per fiscal year based on an informal survey of publication costs posted on publishers' websites at the time. The limit was based on our desire to reasonably allocate available funding rather than a goal to fund a specific number of articles.

Our \$50,000 annual allocation has not changed over the nine years of the author fund. Although some pressure has been alleviated by Read and Publish deals (discussed below), the OA Author Fund nonetheless turns away authors each year. The SCG helps these authors post their articles as post-prints in our repository (green open access), find funding elsewhere, or, if they are early in the submission process, we help authors find a journal that fits their needs.

Opportunity

The fund is viewed as an opportunity to use the library collections budget innovatively and to engender positive associations with the library as a supporter of research, an entity that is current on the technology and trends of publishing, and an advocate for the dissemination of locally produced research. Ideally, the fund should be buying both Creative Commons licensing and goodwill toward the library. Librarians already served as advocates and advisors for copyright and intellectual property concerns by assisting authors with journal selection and reviewing publication contracts: this resource fit into our suite of Research Services. This is a common justification for funding from the library budget rather than another office on university campuses.⁴¹

Selection Criteria

Modeled after several existing funds at peer institutions and with guidance and language from Josh Bolick, a Scholarly Communication Librarian at the University of Kansas, our application process

includes information about publishing, evaluation criteria for journals, and multiple entry points for personal help from the library.⁴² The educational information from our web page and funding criteria may be found in the supplementary materials presented at the conclusion of this article. Applications are reviewed on a rolling basis and decisions are made based on the stated criteria and remaining funding available.

The fund is open to any university-affiliated author, regardless of position, rank, or credit hours. The fund is specifically for journal-length publications and data, including book chapters, but not full books. There is a separate library fund for open textbook and Open Educational Resource funding.

Logistics/workflow

Although each author may apply for up to \$2,000 per fiscal year, multiple university-affiliated authors may apply funding to a single APC. That is, three authors may combine their funding to cover an APC that costs \$5,400.

Paying APCs is time consuming and complicated by the various methods of payment: each transaction follows an individual workflow that often includes signing into a publisher's payment site, paying by institutional bank transfer or by credit card, and tracking individual invoices and receipts. This individual accounting is time consuming, shifting administrative burden onto authors and librarians. Although many libraries bundle APCs into existing payment workflows,⁴³ the diversity of publishers, the speed at which the payments must be made, and the inability of publishers to bundle payments into existing bills mean that at our small library, invoices are paid individually.

Modifications over time

At the beginning of the 2017 fiscal year, the committee decided that the library should only provide funding to pure open access journals and no longer fund hybrid journals. The motivation for this change was to reduce our participation in the act of "double dipping" or allowing publishers to charge libraries twice for the same content: once in subscription fees for the journal or licensed subscription package and a second time in the APCs for a specific article. In the third year of the fund, we believed that it was time to move forward to diminish the amount of our collections budget that supported traditional subscription-based journals. When we informed faculty that their applications could not be funded as we were only funding "pure open access journals," responses were quite negative. These responses are anecdotal based on the fewer than ten rejection emails sent to authors. One author suggested that journal selection was made on factors such as discipline, impact factor, and speed of publication, noting that open access was a low priority. Although these authors were motivated to publish open access to promote discovery in web searches, elevate the work's impact, and increase the number of citations, they worried that pure open access journals were more likely to be new and have a lower impact factor. They also expressed concerns about for profit or predatory journals that did not have the backing of editorial boards or societies. One faculty author wrote that restricting their options for publication funding to pure open access journals was counter to the objective of open access. The response was so negative within the first month that the library reverted to the original criteria for the fund. Because we

had not encountered any negative interactions when turning down applications prior to the change, we decided that the negative impressions from faculty were not worth any educational opportunities that the new restrictions may have sparked.

In 2020, the library signed our first two small Read and Publish deals. These deals converted our subscriptions from purely licensing-to-read agreements to agreements that also allow for open access publishing. The details of each vary as publishers experiment with formats and incentives. The publishing opportunities provided through these deals were added as options in our OA Author Fund application. Over the next three years, the library has considered, negotiated, and signed several Read and Publish deals. These deals, while increasing the number of OA articles published, potentially fund a substantial number of hybrid OA articles. The terms of most of these agreements list eligible journals covered by the publish portion of the deal. The majority of these include both pure and hybrid journals. Although we are actively decreasing spending on hybrid publications via the OA Author Fund, we are separately funding them via agreements with publishers. This is an evolving process, and we will likely continue to adjust our funding each year as new opportunities, funding models, or routes to open are developed.

In July 2020, we altered the OA Author Fund application to make it clear that a portion of the overall fund could be used to pay APCs in “pure open access journals” (60 percent) and a smaller portion (40 percent) could be used to fund “hybrid open access journals.” There have been no complaints, even when funding is denied based on these criteria. Over the next three years, the portion of funding allowed for hybrid journals has decreased and will continue to decrease in the future. Currently, 90 percent of the fund is allocated to pure open access and 10 percent is allocated to hybrid publications.

There have been offers to increase the overall budget for the OA Author Fund from library administration and the university Research Office since 2014. Each time, we have declined the offer. The two main reasons are as follows: (1) It takes a lot of administrative labor to run the fund and we did not wish to increase it, and (2) It would provide further fiscal support of the additional revenue stream that APCs provide for publishers. We have, however, directed authors to their departments, colleges, or the Research Office to ask for funding assistance. The library is currently working with the Research Office to potentially provide additional internal grants to help authors complete scholarly projects. The knowledge we have gained administering the OA Author Fund will greatly inform this possibility.

Methods

This analysis was conducted after nine years of data collection through our OA Author Fund application. Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was granted for this human subjects research as secondary research use of identifiable private information. A copy of the application form is included as an appendix to this paper. Applicants filled out this web-form with information including citation data, acceptance status, their university affiliation, and their motivation for publishing this paper OA. Data was analyzed for descriptive statistics report here and by coding for thematic categories.

Results

The reported results reflect the funded applications for our Author Fund. Unfunded proposals—from phone calls to discuss potential funding, applications for publications that did not meet our criteria, and applications submitted after the fund was exhausted—proved too varied to add context to our results beyond documenting that the desire for funding far surpasses its availability. Most applicants are faculty and graduate students, though staff, undergraduates, post-doctoral fellows, and emeritus faculty have all applied.

Over nine years, \$478,037.76 funded 251 articles with APCs ranging from \$99 to \$5,200. We funded an additional sixty articles through Read and Publish agreements. The average APC was just over \$2,135, and our average payment was \$1,998. The lower actual payment can be attributed to our \$2,000 cap on funding per author and the fact that payment is sometimes split between institutions.

Timing

In the first three years, funds were used up or nearly exhausted by the end of the fiscal year, which runs July 1 through June 30. In year four, funds were exhausted after seven months. Over the next four years, funds were committed before the end of the calendar year (year five: December, year six: September, years seven and eight: November, year nine: December). The clear uptick in requests suggests both that OA publishing has increased, and that knowledge of our fund has spread. The library considered releasing the funding quarterly or narrowing the scope of qualifying manuscripts to attempt to provide funding throughout the year. So far, these ideas have not been implemented.

In response to the open-ended question “Is there any other information we should know?” a minority of applications provided additional information. One theme was the timing of publication: “The journal will not publish the paper until they have received payment” or “We need to pay in the next day or so, as we have received our final proof to approve.” If authors do not apply for our fund until their article is accepted and publishers treat the APC as they might any other invoice, the timing can become problematic. The speed of university approvals and financial processing is often slower than the desired invoice period for publishers. Over the nine years we have been paying APCs, the process has modernized to allow web-based credit card payments which significantly decreases processing time. However, it is common for institutions to prefer to pay such charges from a central office, which can introduce increased time and stress into the process.

External Funding

This fund is not exhaustive of the OA articles published at this university. Many authors pay APCs with grants, startup funding, or funding from co-author’s institutions. Authors also publish in diamond or platinum OA journals that do not charge a fee or make their articles OA through the Green (institutional repository) route. Currently, there is no centralized data on how publishing fees are paid across the university or how much of our content is open. We know that departments, colleges, internal and external grants, and faculty start-up are all used to pay publishing charges. The library is gathering data to increase institutional knowledge of this landscape.

Applicants for the OA Author Fund are asked to declare any funding available to pay APCs, as we wanted our resources to make the most impact in the research ecosystem. Just as funding source reporting is varied and often missing in CrossRef, our data collection on funding varied widely.⁴⁴ In response to the question “Is this work funded in any way? If so, please describe all awards,” 34 percent of applicants listed their funding as they might in the acknowledgments section

of a paper, e.g., “this research was funded in part by a grant from . . .”. Such responses required that we follow-up to determine the amount of funds awarded and the amount needed for open access publishing. Other responses fell into four categories: (1) funded research without publication costs written into the grant (11 percent), (2) funded research where the grant period ended or the funds were fully expended (26 percent), (3) the research was unfunded (20 percent), or (4) the question was unanswered (9 percent).

These responses initially reflected the newness of APCs as a reason that this type of expense was not included in grant budgets. In 2023, though paid OA has become a more mainstream activity, given the timeline of publication in relation to research, it is unrealistic that all research could be funded by grants within a granting period. Communications with individual authors suggested that researchers write publication funds into grants, when possible, though it is unreasonable to assume that researchers will have available funds when APC invoices arrive—sometimes years after the completion of the research.

Value to Researchers

The application included the question “Why is it important for you to make this work open?” We asked this question to gauge the motivations of our authors and potentially track trends over time. Answers were coded into five broad categories with many answers representing more than one category. First, applicants suggested that access, or specifically public and global access, were valuable as a benefit to those without subscription access.

We believe that everyone should be able to access scientific articles.

Second, applicants gave rote answers suggesting the value of their work without referencing the benefits of open access.

Figure 1. Months of available funding from the Open Access Author Fund

Our paper adds to the current state of knowledge regarding the appropriate application of . . . behavior theories to unique cultural populations in which these theories were not developed nor tested in previously. Our results are important because they expand our understanding of the role.

Third, authors desired the increase in visibility, possible citations, or potential impact that OA allows.

Figure 2. Answer to the question "is this work funded in any way?"

[These research subjects] are increasingly being recognized for their potential contributions to biotechnology. Making this article open access will increase its impact, my impact within the field (which is important given my assistant professorship status) and will increase its impact in countries or institutions that cannot pay for journal access fees.

Fourth, authors cited funder requirements or the motivation that research conducted with public funding should be publicly available.

NIH stipulates that all publications resulting from funded research be open access.

And fifth, authors had submitted/been accepted at a pure OA journal and could not move toward publication without APC payments.

This journal is strictly open access; paper will not be published otherwise . . .

Figure 3 outlines distribution of motivation over the nine years of the OA Author Fund. Authors rarely cite funder mandates as part of their OA motivation. No clear trends in motivation appeared over the nine years of the OA Author Fund.

Discussion

The goal of the OA Author Fund was twofold: (1) To fund the publication of articles that otherwise had no access to funding, and (2) To introduce authors to the concept of open access as a positive measure and a benefit to published research. As a measure of our first goal, we have funded 251 articles that likely did not otherwise have easy access to APC funding. While some authors may have had the means to pay an APC without the library's assistance, many do not. Additionally, we feel that

Figure 3. A bar chart depicting the variation in stated motivation for OA publication. Authors primarily cite Access and the value of their research as motivation.

research funding should fund research rather than research dissemination. If the library's OA Author Fund allowed a researcher to pay for an extra month of graduate student research, we consider that a success. Regarding our second goal, it is difficult to disentangle the impact of the OA Author Fund and the overall trend toward open in research: attitudes have shifted over the nine years of this project. We hope that this project has helped to shift local perceptions about OA publishing, yet there are no clear trends in our application information that support that idea. Authors who apply to this fund have already self-selected into a "pro-open" category. It is reasonable to assume that the OA Author Fund has been one of many positive inputs that has helped shape some researcher's feelings about and motivation around open access, though we have not collected data to isolate those inputs and their impacts.

Of the roughly 700 authors and co-authors involved in these 251 publications, 166 authors were listed on at least two papers. Table 1 shows the rate of repeat funding for authors and co-authors.

It is hard to draw concrete conclusions from these numbers, though the seventeen authors who appear on five or more funded papers are all tenured faculty who publish often and have multiple co-authors, collaborative works, and graduate students. We have done some outreach to publicize this fund, though most of our applications come at point of need or through word of mouth. It is clear from interactions with applicants that many have heard about the fund from co-authors, advisors, research support staff, or colleagues. We have relied on this type of communication to spread knowledge of the fund. As evidenced by the chart below, we have supported papers from thirty departments on campus.

The chart of funding by department includes the sixty articles funded through our Read and Publish agreements for a total of 311 published articles. About a fifth of the articles have co-authors from multiple departments. Some departments are more heavily represented in this pool.

This data suggests that we could be doing more outreach some departments, though it follows a similar pattern to the overall university publication rate as seen in figure 4.

Table 1. Rate of repeat funding for authors

Number of times the author was on a funded paper	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Number of authors funded at rate	528	89	45	16	5	3	3	2	3	1

Figure 4. Funding rate by department by year for FY15-FY23.

If we examine the change in the rate of applications from year to year, there are more authors considering providing open access to their publications. We know that this funding has had direct impact on 251 articles, provided positive library interactions for those author teams, and prompted many conversations regarding author’s rights, APC rates, journal selection criteria, and the value of prestige in publishing. Based on our initial goals, this OA Author Fund has been a success.

On a broader scale, we must question whether this sort of fund has a lasting impact on the scholarly landscape. Although an OA Author Fund can change some researchers’ ideas about openness in publishing, it may not shift researchers’ publishing practices beyond the specific instance of funding.

Hybrid OA improves access while supporting current power structures. This piecemeal payment of funds from the library, from individuals, from research groups and labs, and from funders is distributed and uncoordinated enough to allow no leverage on the author side and thus no strategy that could benefit authors or payees. This practice has become costly and allows the publishing industry to financially exploit the academic needs of authors.⁴⁵

The library still views the OA Author Fund and our Read and Publish deals as a benefit to campus. Although our collections budget allows for this type of spending, we will likely continue to evolve our fiscal support for OA publishing. We assess our funding opportunities as part of the budgeting process each spring and are grateful to have both the budget and support to try new OA funding models. We will also continue to provide outreach and education about the OA publishing options that authors have and, hopefully, continue to develop connections and trust with our university authors.

Figure 5. Publication authorship by department 2014-2023.

Limitations

The ability to subsidize article processing charges is dependent on available budget options. Without the flexibility of institutional funding, this type of project is not possible. Libraries should examine budget constraints and strategic goals, as well as campus climate, when considering such a fund. Education should include the nuances of both paid and unpaid OA options, potential avenues for authors to retain their rights, and resources to help authors publish in journals that fit their specific needs.

The OA Author Fund does not function well as tool for education about publication options for accepted articles. Our criteria suggest that articles should already be accepted: therefore, if a journal does not fit our standards, it is too late to have a meaningful conversation about journal selection or alternative OA options.

We innately perceive value and cost as interwoven. We cannot extricate prestige and cost without radically changing the system of promotion and advancement in academia.⁴⁶ Although it is unimaginable for some to spend \$5,200 on a single publication, others would absolutely pay and feel that they are gaining value by expending those funds.

Conclusions

As Plan S makes the shift away from supporting Read and Publish deals and moves to encouraging “pure publish” deals in 2024, there may be dozens of new avenues to work with publishers to open access to literature.⁴⁷ We must critically analyze each before adopting it.⁴⁸

In the incremental push toward a more open publishing landscape, a publication fund that focuses on OA publishing may allow libraries to be agile while promoting open publishing practices. Such a fund may lack the newsworthiness of a transformative deal, yet still allows for the cultural transformation that is a key component in the OA movement. These funds allow institutions with lower or more varied publication practices to support their authors and act in line with their values rather than being locked into multi-year contracts. An OA Author Fund or innovation fund allows flexibility within library budgets as financial circumstances and priorities change.

The role of APCs should be transitional. It should be educational, limited, and serve to provide access to knowledge. Open advocates should neither become complacent nor should they lose motivation when the scholarly publishing system resists change. The goal is open, equitable access to knowledge. While the means will change over time, the long-term goals of a more financially sustainable, globally equitable publication model should remain in focus. Our OA Author Fund was developed to support the transition to open through financial support and normalizing open access publishing. Based on these parameters, our OA Author Fund is a successful project.

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Supplementary Materials

Questions Asked in the OA Author Fund Application

1. Name of author (or authors) and their affiliations*
2. Paper title*
3. Journal Name*
4. Publisher*
5. Is this journal a hybrid journal or a pure open access journal?*
6. Definitions: In the gold OA model, all articles and related content are available for free immediately on the journal's website through payment of an Article Processing Charge (APC). Hybrid open access journals contain a mixture of open access articles (paid by APCs) and closed access articles. A publisher following this model is partially funded by subscriptions, and only provide open access for those individual articles for which the authors (or research sponsor) pay a publication fee. If you have questions please contact . . .
7. Link to published Data
8. Data repository
9. Cost of providing open access to this work
10. Is this work funded in any way? If so, please describe all awards.
11. Why is it important for you to make this work open?*
12. Is there any other information we should know?
13. What is the name of your department?*
14. Is this work accepted for publication?*
15. If No, please explain the status of the item.
16. Author's email*
17. Author's phone number

* indicates required question.

Accepted Articles from 2014 to 2023

Available at Leila Sterman, "MSU OA Author Fund Supported Papers 2014–2023," data set, 2024, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10908990>.